

ECHOES of the past: recreating lost soundscapes for a digital touring experience in the Old Town of Xanthi, Greece

Despoina Tsiafaki, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4948-255X>

Natasa Michailidou, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0049-5560>

Dimitris Kalogiannidis, <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7571-7586>

Melpomeni Karta, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8302-5665>

Akrivi Katifori, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6755-2836>

Katerina Servi, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1866-5871>

Maria Boile, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8330-4696>

Yannis Ioannidis, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1705-8247>

Culture and Creative Industries Department, 'Athena' Research Center, Xanthi, Greece

Contact: amixaili@athenarc.gr

The concept of soundscapes, referring to the “sonic environment” of a society (Schafer 1994, 274-75), a combination of sound, space and the individual (Graham, Eve, and Pantos 2019, 228), when applied to heritage, can promote a deeper understanding of the historical context and everyday life during different periods. In comparison to visual reconstructions, the reconstruction of the sounds of the past has been significantly less researched and applied in practice. The use of sounds in sightseeing tour applications is often limited to audio descriptions of landscapes, monuments, historical personalities, events etc. Soundscapes, however, can provide insights into how people experienced their environment. Advances in audio technology enable us to tackle the ephemeral character of sounds, and analyze and present them in new and remarkable ways.

This paper will discuss the research on the formation and use of soundscapes for the recreation of everyday life in the old town of Xanthi in Greece, through a freely available digital touring application. This app will be developed within the two-and-a-half-year research project ECHOES (funded by the EU’s “Greece 2.0 - National Recovery and Resilience Plan” and implemented since mid-2022 by a consortium consisting of the “Athena” Research Center, the cultural company MENTOR, and the sound production company Rabbeats: <https://www.ilsp.gr/en/projects/echoes-en/>).

It will present the research and technology pathways taken to unveil, to locals and visitors of Xanthi, a) aspects of better and lesser known people of the city; b) the different religious communities coexisting in the town; c) the built environment for which the old town of Xanthi is famous; and d) the ‘golden’ era of Xanthi, dating from the late 19th to the early 20th century, which in certain ways is still visible in the modern city. Making use of the scarce archives and local publications, we try to see if recreated soundscapes (of, for instance, 1870 or 1899) can help the visitor forge a deeper connection with the past. By acknowledging the cultural and social construction of sound, soundscapes, understood as an analytical tool, provide a gateway to history (Thompson 2002).

The presentation will focus on the requirements for analysis and how it informs the conceptual, theoretical, and technological approach adopted, while researching content and designing a soundscape-based experience. From a technological standpoint, the audio-augmented walking tour will be available through a web-based or native mobile application. Audio points will be assigned a specific location and different attributes at the authoring stage of the experience, determining the way audio points are prioritized and handled during the tour. The application will track the user's location and play any audio detected within a predefined search radius.

The ECHOES of Xanthi's past will be unveiled through different sounds, stemming from commercial places, educational and religious institutions, administrative buildings, etc. The user of the application will have the opportunity to tour the old town, interacting with the social and cultural landscapes of a bygone era and experiencing aspects of the lives of the people who made up the colorful mosaic of the city.

References:

Graham, Shawn, Stuart Eve, and Alexis Pantos. 2019. "Hearing the Past." *Seeing the Past with Computers: Experiments with Augmented Reality and Computer Vision for History*, edited by Kevin Kee and Timothy J. Compeau, 224-36. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press.

<https://doi.org/10.3998/mpub.9964786>.

Schafer, Murray R. 1994. *The Soundscape: Our Sonic Environment and the Tuning of the World*. Rochester, Vermont: Destiny Books.

Thompson, Emily. 2002. *The Soundscape of Modernity: Architectural Acoustics and the Culture of Listening in America, 1900-1933*. Cambridge, MA, and London: MIT Press.